

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
MSc. PROGRAM IN HORTICULTURE

**INFLUENCE OF PRE-HARVEST TREATMENTS ON POST HARVEST QUALITY
AND SHELF LIFE OF ONION (*Allium cepa* L.) VARIETIES IN BAHIR DAR ZURIA
DISTRICT, AMHARA REGION**

M.Sc. Thesis

By

Fentahun Assefa

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Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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**SUBMITTED IN THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR
THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE (M.SC.) IN “HORTICULTURE”**

Major Advisor: Professor Melkamu Alemayehu

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THESIS APPROVAL SHEET

As member of the Board of Examiners of the Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) thesis open defense examination, we have read and evaluated this thesis prepared by Mr. **Fentahun Assefa** entitled “**Influence of Pre-Harvest Treatments on Post-Harvest Quality and Shelf life of Onion (*Allium Cepa* L.) Varieties in Bahir Dar Zuria District, Amhara Region**”. We hereby certify that the thesis is accepted for fulfilling the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) in Horticulture.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Influence of Pre-Harvest Treatments on Post-Harvest Quality and Shelf life of Onion (*Allium Cepa* L.) Varieties in Bahir Dar Zuria District, Amhara Region**” Submitted to in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of sciences M.Sc., in “Horticulture” to the department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University, by **Mr. Fentahun Assefa**, ID.No. BDU1401211 is an authentic work carried out by him under our guidance. The matter embodied in this thesis work has not been submitted earlier for the award of any degree or diploma to the best of our knowledge and belief.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my beloved family who sacrificed everything to ensure my better future bright, wellbeing and welfare.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CGR	Cumulative Growth rate
CV	Coefficient of variation
EIAR	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAOSTAT	Food and Agricultural Organization Statistics
GSARS	Global Strategy Agricultural Rural Statistics
LSD	Least Significance Difference
MOA	Ministry of Agriculture
MOARD	Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development
OPV	Open Pollinated Varieties
RCBD	Randomized Complete Block Design
RGR	Relative growth rate
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
SE	Standard error
TDM	Total dry matter
TSP	Triple super phosphate
TSS	Total Soluble Solid

Influence of Pre-Harvest Treatments on Post-Harvest Quality and Shelf life of Onion

(Allium Cepa L.) Varieties in Bahir Dar Zuria District, Amhara Region

By: Fentahun Assefa

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ABSTRACT

*Onion is the most important and widely cultivated bulb vegetable in Ethiopia. High postharvest loss during storage is one of the main challenges of onion production and productivity. The present study was therefore conducted with the aim of evaluating the effects of selected pre-harvest treatments on shelf life and postharvest quality of onion varieties in diffused light storage structure. The bulbs of three hybrid (Red coach, Russet, Jambar) and one open-pollinated (Bombay red) varieties produced in Woramit Research Site of ARARI during the 2023 irrigation season using uniform and standard agronomic practices. The pre-harvest treatments were toppling at 70% neck fall with (easy of pulling up) and without irrigation, toppling at 90% neck fall, and harvesting at 70% neck fall without toppling. Moreover, the postharvest parameters of bulbs were collected at 0th, 4th, 8th and 12th week of storage. Accordingly, the treatments were arranged with 4*4*4 factorial combination in RCBD with three replications in the storage experiment. Based on the treatment setup, bulbs were stored in DLS in Zenzelema campus of Bahir Dar University for three months. Data on postharvest quality parameters were collected and analyzed using mixed model combined analysis SAS (version 9.4) software where pre-harvest treatment and variety were considered as fixed variables while storage duration was considered as random variable. The results of combined analysis of variance revealed that variety, pre harvest treatment and storage duration influenced most of the tested parameters of onion in the storage. Similarly, the interaction of variety and pre harvest treatments influenced decay percentage ($P<0.001$), bulb firmness ($P<0.001$), total soluble solid of onion bulbs ($P<0.0001$) and marketable bulbs yield ($P<0.001$) throughout the storage duration. The varieties Jambar and Russet and the practice of toppling at 90% maturity recorded the lowest sprouting and weight loss percentage of onion bulbs in the storage and highest proportion of marketable bulbs highest bulb firmness. On the other hand Bombay red variety, toppled at 70% maturity followed by irrigation recorded the highest sprouting, decay percentage, bulb weight loss and the lowest bulb firmness. It is conclude that the use of Jambar and Russet varieties and the practice of toppling at 90% maturity are therefore suggested to maintain the quality and reduce postharvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage. As the study is limited to single location and season, it is recommended to repeat the study in multiplications and seasons.*

Key words: Onion, Hybrid varieties, Shelf life, Toppling, Yield

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Justification

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) belongs to the family Alliaceae, and it is an important bulb crop cultivated in tropical and subtropical parts of the world. It ranks second next to tomato in terms of income generation among vegetables (FAO, 2022). It is probably originated in central Asia between Turkmenistan and Afghanistan where some of its relatives still grow as wild plants (El-Samad *et al.*, 2011). The genus *Allium* contains about 750 species, among these onion, leeks and garlic are the most important ones (Weldemariam Seifu *et al.*, 2015). It is herbaceous biennial but cultivated as an annual crop for its bulb production while it takes two seasons for its seed production. Onion is monocotyledonous, cross-pollinated, having diploid chromosomes number $2n=16$ (Bassett, 1986). It is cool season bulb vegetable crop (Boukary *et al.*, 2012).

Onion is an important vegetable crop which has been produced in at least 261 countries of the world (FAOSTAT, 2017) including Ethiopia for its daily uses and economic benefits. It is rich in minerals, carbohydrates, proteins and vitamin C and other sulphur-containing compounds. These compounds are responsible for pungency, odours and many of health promoting effects includes anti-carcinogenic properties, antibiotics effects, anti-allergenic and anti-bacterial potential (Trivedi and Dhumal, 2013). Onions are used in different ways, such as being eaten fresh, used for food flavoring, or included as the main ingredient in many recipes (Huang, *et al.*, 2022). Onions contain antioxidants which keep lifestyle-related diseases in check; thus, they are a vital component of a balanced diet (Ouyang *et al.*, 2018). Onion is an important cash crop for Ethiopian farmers. It is a source of income and creates employment opportunities in different parts of the country (Lemma *et al.*, 2006). The crop is produced for local consumption and regional export market (Griffith's *et al.*, 2002).

Onion production in Ethiopia is associated with relatively high postharvest losses expressed in terms of sprouting, rotting and weight loss of the bulbs (Ferreira *et al.*, 2017). According to Tripathi and Lawande (2019), postharvest losses of onion comprise of 8-10, 10-12, and 30-40% due to sprouting, rotting and weight loss respectively under improper storage facilities

for 4 to 5 months. Postharvest loss depends on the genotype, production and postharvest handling practices and storage conditions (Romo, 2021). Postharvest loss of 40% to 50% of onion was also reported by different scholars (Ortola and Knox, 2015; Gorreapti *et al.* 2017, Sule 2019). Similarly, Barrett *et al.* (2023) reported postharvest loss of onion in the range of 20% to 50%, with notable losses occurring during production practices, harvesting, storage and transit. In Ethiopia the post-harvest loss of onion is estimated to be 13-36 % in Meki and Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (Hanna Daniels and Fors, 2015). In north-western Ethiopia, 29.7% of onion postharvest loss was observed along the supply chain due to improper application of pre-and postharvest handling practices (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

Pre-harvest practices such as irrigation management, variety selection, stage of maturity and toppling of onion plants before harvesting significantly impact the shelf life and post-harvest quality of onion crops. Selecting onion varieties with traits such as thick outer skins and enhanced storage capabilities reduce vulnerability to mechanical damage and storage decay that in turn reduces postharvest losses (Mahajan *et al.*, 2017). Onion cultivars vary greatly in their inherited storage ability, so correct cultivar choice is essential for successful storage (Rabinowitch and Currah, 2002). In this regard, the production of hybrid varieties is vital to increase both the productivity and shelf life of onion.

Harvesting onion bulbs at appropriate maturity stage and practicing toppling along with appropriate irrigation scheduling significantly influence the quality and storability of onion bulbs (Wills *et al.*, 2016). Onion is matured when 70% to 90% of the plants are fallen and the leaves turn yellow and dried (Jan, 2021). Sprouting, weight loss and firmness are the primary parameters of onion that are affected by inappropriate maturity at the time of harvesting (Kader, 2002). Similarly, the practice of toppling of onion plants along with irrigation scheduling influences the shelf life and postharvest losses of onion bulbs (Wills *et al.*, 2016). Toppling in onion production is a specific cultural practice that involves bending the onion tops (foliage) over to encourage bulb development and improve bulb quality. This practice redirects energy from leaf growth towards bulb formation. Additionally, toppling discourages seed stalk formation (bolting), which can reduce bulb quality (Lewis and Anderson, 2015). Typically toppling is performed around two to three weeks before harvesting or when the

onion tops are about 70% to 90% fallen over naturally and reached maturity or the tops begin turn yellow (Lewis and Anderson, 2015; Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

Irrigation management significantly influences the postharvest quality and shelf life of onion bulbs. The timing for stopping irrigation before harvesting onions can vary based on factors such as soil moisture, weather conditions, and onion variety. However, a common practice is to stop irrigation approximately two to three weeks before harvesting. Proper irrigation management significantly impacts onion production and post-harvest quality. Research findings by Bramhane *et al.* (2022) suggest that stopping irrigation 3 weeks before harvest yield favorable results. Sharma *et al.* (2020) also highlighted that excessive irrigation during bulb development can lead to increased water content in the bulbs, making them more susceptible to rot and decay during storage. Conversely, deficit irrigation or stopping irrigation before harvesting helps promote bulb maturity, enhances bulb curing, and reduces postharvest losses.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Onion's production in Northwest Ethiopia is significant, playing a crucial role in the livelihoods of farmers and the regional economy. It is one of the principal cash crops cultivated in the region, has a great contribution substantially to agricultural income, food security, economic and health issues ranging from smallholder farmer to large-scale commercial farms (Habtamu Mossie, 2020). The production and productivity of onion in Ethiopia in general and in the study area in particular is very low due to insufficient availability of quality seeds, technologies, inappropriate cultural practices, inappropriate pre and postharvest handling practices (Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.*, 2015, Nikus Olani and Fikre Mulugeta, 2010). Among cultural practices, in appropriate pre-harvest treatments applications such as toppling, and applying irrigation water at the time of harvesting are the main ones, (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

Toppling, when prolonged, may inadvertently expose bulbs to adverse environmental conditions, such as sunburn and pest infestations, thereby compromising postharvest quality. However, when implemented carefully, toppling can facilitate bulb curing and enhance storage longevity. Appropriate toppling practices may offer benefits in terms of bulb development and yield; they may also introduce risks that compromise postharvest quality (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, further research efforts on crop management and postharvest handling practice are required to clarify optimal pre harvest treatments.

The implications of irrigation water application during harvesting and the timing and amount of irrigation during harvesting can influence bulb texture, susceptibility to decay, and overall marketability (Patil *et al.* 2018). Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.* (2023) also indicated that some farmers were irrigate their onion fields at the critical stage of harvesting, excessive moisture content in the bulbs may influence bulb quality. Similarly, the adjustment of irrigation frequency by farmers during the harvesting period has been noted as a notable factor affecting postharvest quality. While some farmers reduce irrigation frequency to promote bulb maturation and reduce moisture-related issues, others maintain regular irrigation schedules to mitigate stress on the crop. The impact of irrigation frequency on bulb size, firmness, and

susceptibility to diseases underscores the need for careful management practices the practice of toppling onions for extended durations, varying from one farmer to another.

Although onion is one of the cash crops of smallholder farmers produced under irrigation in Bahir Dar Zuria district of Amhara Region like any other parts of the country, its postharvest loss is high, which negatively influences the incomes of farmers. Farmers in the study area are using open-pollinated onion varieties that have low yielding capacities and limited storability. In this regard, Rahman *et al.* (2007) reported that postharvest loss and short shelf life is a serious challenge of open-pollinated onion varieties which could reach up to 100%. Poor storability of onion bulbs forces the farmers to sell their products soon after harvest when the price is relatively low because of surplus production (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

Traditionally, some onion growers in Ethiopia including the study area are practicing toppling/bending of onion plants by legs or using wooden plank to facilitate bulb-neck drying before harvesting. On the other hand some other farmers are irrigating onion plants some days before harvesting for ease of harvesting (hand pulling) processes (Alemu Melaku, 2015) . The effects of these agronomic practices on the postharvest loss and shelf life of onion bulbs is however not well studied. Therefore, the present study was initiated to evaluate the effect of different pre-harvest treatments on shelf life and postharvest quality of hybrid onion varieties.

1.3. Objectives

1.3.1. General objective

- ❖ The general objective of the present study was contributing for the reduction of postharvest loss by implementing appropriate pre-harvest management practices and identifying onion variety with prolonged shelf life.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

- To identify the effects of pre-harvest treatment and onion variety on the postharvest quality and shelf life of onion.
- To identify the appropriate pre-harvest agronomic practices and the variety in terms of

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Description of Onion

The primary origin of onion is Central Asia with secondary center in Middle East and Mediterranean Region (Zohary and Hopf, 2000, Grubben and Denton, 2004). Onions are one of the most ancient vegetable crops under cultivation. Onions have been widely distributed to various countries of the world. Onion is an herbaceous monocot plant, which is cultivated as an annual crop for the purpose of bulb production. However, it is cultivated as a biennial crop for seed production. During the first season, bulbs are formed while flower stalks and seeds are developed in the second season (Corgan *et al.*, 2000).

It is a cross pollinated and cool season crop having diploid chromosomes number ($2n=16$) (Bassett, 1986). Recent estimations accept about 750 species in the genus *Allium*, among which onion, Japanese bunching onion, leek and garlic are the most important edible *Allium* crops (Rabinowitch and Currah, 2002). Onion has a shallow root or short lived, being continuously produced, rarely have branches, and root hairs, and rarely increase in diameter.

The onion bulb is composed of fleshy enlarged leaf base or scale and small conical stem (Shanmugasundaram and Kalib, 2001). The bulb varies from flat to round. Leaves are long, round and hollow. Leaf initiation stops when the plant begins to bulb. The base of each leaf becomes one of the scales of the onion bulb, so that the final bulb size depends on the number of leaves present at bulb initiation. Flowers are small and formed at the terminal tip of the stems as umbels (Hamasaki *et al.*, 1999). Seeds are smooth, black, wrinkled when dry; embryo curved, germinate epigeal. Fruits capsule in shape and splitting longitudinally (Tindall, 1983; Mallor *et al.*, 2011). Major bulb features are uniformity of shape, size and skin color, pungency, and dry matter (Rabinowitch and Brewster, 1990; Rubatzky and Yamaguchi, 1996).

2.2. Importance of Onion

Onion is one of the most important bulb vegetables cultivated commercially in most parts of the world. They are primarily consumed for their unique flavor or for their ability to enhance the flavor of other foods. The major flavor of alliums results from the activity of the enzymes, alliinase, acting on certain sulfur-containing compounds (S-alkyl cysteine sulfoxides) when tissues are broken or crushed. It has a distinctive flavor, pungency, is eaten as fried, boiled, roasted or raw in salad as vegetable, and is widely used as a condiment in preparation of soups, savory dish, canned food product, salads and sandwiches. Moreover, it is also processed as pickle, chutney, and sauces and consumed in dehydrated form (Muhammad S. J, 2004).

The mature onion bulb contains some starch, appreciable quantities of sugars, some protein, and vitamins A, B, and moreover, onion has medicinal importance because of its anticarcinogenic, antibiotic properties and anti-platelet activities (Griffith's *et al.*, 2002). The antibacterial activity of onion can be attributed to the presence of flavonoids and polyphenols which has been reported to have broad spectrum of antibacterial activity. Flavonoids are not only anti-bacterial, but also known to be anti-cancer, antiviral, anti-allergenic and anti-inflammatory. Onions can be considered as a good source of natural additives to retard food deterioration. The production of onion is becoming an important source of income, improved food security and employment opportunity (Lemma *et al.*, 2006).

2.3. Environmental Requirement of Onion

Onion is a cool season crop that has some frost tolerance. Bulb formation requires high temperatures, while the early stages of onion growth require low temperatures (Jilani *et al.*, 2004). Optimum temperature for production of onion ranges from 18 to 27°C. Temperatures below the optimum ranges caused bolting of plants consequently reduced bulb yield. Similarly, temperatures above 30°C led to early maturity of the plant and reduced bulb yield.

Onion bulbs grow faster at warmer temperatures than cooler temperatures (Raemaekers, 2001).

Bulb growth and development are both influenced by temperature and photoperiod, bulb formation being promoted by long days and high temperatures (Jilani and Ghaffoor, 2004). Cool conditions are usually required during the first part of the season, when the plants starting to form bulbs. Warm and dry weather is needed for harvesting and curing (Savva and Frenken, 2002). Relatively high temperature and long photoperiod are required for bulb formation and for seed production. Light intensity, light quality and light duration interact with temperature influences the bulb formation process of onion. In warm weather and bright day's onion forming bulbs at shorter day lengths (Hamasaki *et al.*, 1999).

Onions can grow between 500 and 2400 meters above sea level. Nevertheless, according to (Lemma Desalegne and Herath (1994), the best growing altitude in Ethiopia is between 700 and 1800 m above sea level. Bulb storability is highly influenced by high relative humidity. When relative humidity is high, post-harvest bulbs will sprout and rot which further reduces the marketable yield of onion. The soils used for onions range from light sands to heavy clay loams. Peat soils or sandy soils, if irrigation is available, are preferred and often used. Adequate moisture is critical for uniform seedling emergence. Soils with high water holding capacity are better able to provide moisture to the shallow rooting system but must also drain well to be suitable.

Growth is retarded when available soil moisture is low, but onions are also sensitive to a high-water table or water logging. Uniform moisture availability of about 400-800mm per crop is conducive to large bulb size and high yields. Onion is sensitive to highly acid soils and grows best when the pH is between 6.5 and 8.0 (Savva and Frenken, 2002).

2.4. Potential and Constraints of Onion Production in Ethiopia

Ethiopia including Amhara Region has diverse agro-ecologies that enable to produce tropical, subtropical, and temperate vegetables including onion throughout the year (Kubsa *et al.*, 2006). The country has a great potential to produce onion throughout the year both for local

consumption and for export because of presence of underground and surface water potential, which can be used to produce horticultural crops including onion (Selesh Bekele, 2010). The existence of abundant cultivable land and fertile soils makes the country suitable for commercial production of onion. The increasing demand in domestic, regional and export market can be also considered as an important opportunity for farmers in Ethiopia including in Amhara region to produce onion, since the country is near to the regional and world market (Joosten *et al.*, 2011).

The production and productivity of vegetable crops including onion in Ethiopia as well as in the study area is very low. This is due to insufficient availability of quality seeds, technologies used and inappropriate cultural practices (Nikus Olani and Fikre Mulugeta, 2010).

In addition, since most of the time onion is produced by smallholder farmers, traditional farming system, lack of agricultural inputs such as fertilizer, improved varieties, and pesticides as well as inappropriate pre and postharvest handling practices are the major constraints of onion production that leads to low production and productivity (Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.*, 2015).

Furthermore, due to favorable tropical conditions in Ethiopia, which favor the development of pests, onion is suffering from various diseases and insect pests throughout the country including in the study area. The most common diseases occurred in Ethiopian onion farms are purple blotch, onion neck rot and powdery mildew, which are caused by the fungi *Alternaria porri*, *Botrytis cineraria* and *Peronospora destructor*, respectively (Lemma Dessalegn and Shimelis Aklilu, 2003). Among insect pests, thrips, mites and cutworms are the most important ones in farmer's onion farms (Lemma Dessalegn, 2004). The damages caused by pests are further increased because most onion-growing farmers do not use the exact pesticides and the recommended rates for the control of pests (Edossa Etissa, 2013).

Poor infrastructures such as rural roads and communication for efficient flow of goods and market information are another constraint, where most onion production sites are not accessible for transportation. As onions are perishable by nature, they cannot be stored for

long period without quality decline unless properly handled. Moreover, there is a serious problem in the marketing of horticultural crops including onion in Ethiopia in general and in the study area in particular which affect not only the incomes negatively but also the interests of farmers to participate in the onion production in the following years (Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.*, 2015).

So far, research activities in Ethiopia were mainly focused on the identification of superior cultivars of onions and adopting improved management practices. Little emphasis was given to extending storability of onion. Onion cultivars vary greatly in their inherited storage ability, so correct cultivar choice is essential for successful storage (Rabinowitch and Currah, 2002). Thus, the selection of varieties that have high yielder and longer storage life is one of the best practices for reducing storage losses. It is imperative to choose a variety having good yield and storage to augment the storage life with minimum losses.

Growers in the study area produced improved onion varieties, mainly Bombay red and Adama Red. Although the growers produced improved onion varieties still now the productivity and shelf life are remained low in the study area. So, different hybrid onion varieties have been allowed to introduce from abroad into Ethiopia by different production companies and registered by ministry of agriculture (Beshir Bedru, 2019). Hybrid onion varieties are wider adaptable, produce higher bulb yield, have better shelf life and should be an alternative to enhance the productivity and shelf life of onion in the study area. However, information about the suitability of hybrid onion varieties, yield performance and shelf life in the study area is limited. Therefore, evaluation of these high yielding hybrid onion varieties for postharvest quality and shelf life is essential.

2.5. Effects of Pre-Harvest Treatment on Postharvest Quality of Onion

2.5.1. Effect of toppling and harvesting stages on postharvest quality and shelf life of onion

Pre-harvest toppling is the process of bending onion tops to the ground level at the time of maturity by legs or using wooden plank to initiate neck-drying, reduction of moisture content

and promote uniform drying of outer layers. Pre-harvest toppling and irrigation can have a significant impact on onion postharvest quality and shelf life of onion (Eshghi *et al.*, 2022). Pre-harvest toppling, when strategically implemented, has shown potential for reducing postharvest losses and enhancing onion quality. Kumar *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that pre-harvest toppling resulted in decreased weight loss, improved onion firmness, reduced incidence of onion diseases, extended onion shelf life, lowered respiration rates, and maintained optimal water content levels. The study also found that pre-harvest toppling reduced onion sugar content and increased onion enzyme activity. In general, to maximize yield and quality, onions should be harvested only when the leaves have fallen naturally. The bulbing phase is often very rapid and occurs near the end of the onion's active growth period. During this time, the onion tops will begin to fall over and die.

The effect of toppling and harvesting stages on the postharvest storage and shelf life of onions is a topic of interest in agricultural research. However, specific studies focusing on toppling are not readily available. However, a study on garlic, which is closely related to onions, found that harvesting at 80% top fall, curing, and storing bulbs on a shelf or in a net bag leads to good yield and postharvest quality and effective storability of garlic bulbs under ambient storage conditions (Adamicki, 2004).

Harvesting stage is one of the cultural practices being investigated in the management of bulb onion postharvest quality (Wright *et al.*, 2001). Onion bulbs are matured when the tops (foliage) become yellow and begin to fall over. The percentage of fallen tops during harvesting influences the post-harvest quality and shelf life of onion. In this regard, research results reported that altering the harvesting stages reduces the incidence of postharvest disease and maintains the quality of bulbs in storage for longer time (Akrofi *et al.*, 2016). Onion bulbs harvested at 80-100% leaf drop results in less skin cracks while accommodating roughly 10 cm neck above the bulb (Eshel *et al.*, 2014). According to Kiura *et al.* (2021) onion bulbs harvested at 75% top fall and cured for one or 2 weeks before topping was found to have apparently better visual and keeping quality. Early harvesting before 50% maturity and delayed harvesting after a full maturity increase the sprouting of onion bulbs (Suojala, 2001). According to the author, onion can be harvested between 50% maturity and 100% neck fall

for medium and long-term storage without sacrificing storage quality. Due to fewer outer scales and higher moisture content immature bulbs requires longer curing period (> a week) than mature onion (Gorreapti *et al.*, 2017). Similar to onion, the storage life of garlic is also influenced by the harvesting stage of the crop. The highest sprouting percentage of garlic was recorded from bulbs harvested at 60% top fall and non-cured bulbs, while the least sprouting was observed in 80% top fall and cured bulbs (Bizuayehu Desta *et al.*, 2021). In another research finding, garlic bulbs harvested at 75% top fall recorded the low incidence of skin rot, lower weight loss, and more marketable grades (Sebsebe Woldetsadik and Seyoum Workneh, 2010). Determination of the optimum harvest maturity stage is necessary to reduce postharvest losses of onion in the storage.

2.5.2. Effects of irrigation practices on shelf life and post-harvest quality of onion

The amount and frequency of irrigation water influences the yield and postharvest quality of onions (Kumar *et al.*, 2007). Excessive and/or too frequent watering can cause a reduction in storability of onion bulbs by increasing rotting and sprouting (Pejić *et al.*, 2011; Ortola and Knox, 2015). Researchers have investigated that increasing irrigation frequency using surface irrigation can increase storage losses (Biswas *et al.*, 2010). The ideal onion water needs can be covered by irrigating the soil to a depth of an inch (2.5 cm.) once a week. On the other hand, water stress during crop growth can affect onion bulb size, marketable quality, and post-harvest health and storability (Miller. and Shock, 1992; Terán-Chaves, *et al.*, 2023).

It was reported that onion seasonal water requirements are highly variable depending on agro climate, location and season (Ortola and Knox. 2015), as are the crop coefficients (Kc) which range from 0.4 to 0.7 (initial stage), 0.85 to 1.05 (middle development) and 0.6 to 0.75 (final stage). The same authors reported that seasonal irrigation needs vary from 225 to 1040 mm to produce between 10 and 77 Mg ha⁻¹. Generally, 75–100% evapotranspiration (ETC) is required for better yield and storability of onion bulbs. The increased initial moisture content in onion bulb could explain the larger weight loss. It inhibits rot and sprouting during storage when the soil is kept moist with good irrigation until 2 weeks before harvest mainly due to minimal physiological processes within the crop (de Santa Olalla *et al.*, 2004).

Irrigation should be stopped two weeks prior to onion harvesting. Irrigation after maturity significantly impacts post-harvest quality onion bulbs. Studies have shown that withholding water during the final crop development stage can lead to regrowth, excess bulb moisture, and increased drying costs for storage (Miller. and Shock, 1992; Terán-Chaves, *et al*, 2023).

2.5.3. Effects of varieties on post-harvest quality and shelf life of onion

Onion varieties differ in their suitability for storage and have different storage life. In the study conducted by Kahsay *et al.* (2013). In experiment conducted by Ansari (2007) in Bangladesh the varieties Taxes yellow Grano, Taxes Early Grano and G1 had the shortest storage life compared to other varieties in which about 50% of the stocks were destroyed after 60 days. Higher respiration with generation of heat promotes the onion re-growth during storage and it also increases moisture loss from the bulb and thus reduced shelf life (Benkeblia *et al.*, 2003).

Hybrid onion varieties have gained significant attention in recent years due to their potential for higher yield and improved post-harvest quality. By evaluating different hybrid onion varieties and implementing appropriate pre-harvest treatments, researchers aim to determine their impact on overall yield and post-harvest quality, maximizing productivity, reducing post-harvest losses, and promoting the sustainability and economic viability of the onion industry in Ethiopia. Ethiopia can harness the full potential of its onion production, contribute to food security and rural development, and establish a competitive position in the global onion market.

Through research and experimentation, scientists can assess the performance of various hybrid onion varieties in terms of both yield and post-harvest quality. This will allow them to identify which varieties are most suitable for cultivation, and which pre-harvest treatments yield the best results in terms of maintaining quality and extending the shelf life of the onions (Adamicki, 2004). To enhance the onion industry in Ethiopia, it is crucial to evaluate and

adopt hybrid onion varieties and implement effective pre-harvest treatments (Yebirzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2023).

CHAPTER THREE: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the Study Area

Onion plants were grown in Bahir Dar Zuria districts at Woramit Horticultural Crops Training and Testing site during the 2023 irrigation season where the pre-harvest treatments were superimposed. Bahir Dar Zuria district is located around Bahir Dar town, within 29° 27' 34", 35° 58' 40" East of longitude and 13° 38' 19', 12° 1' 37" North of latitude. The mean altitude of the district is 1,800 meter above sea level and the temperature of the district ranges from 10 to 38 °C throughout the year with mean annual rainfall of 750 mm. The storage experiment was carried out in the storage room of the Bahir Dar University College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (Zenzelema Campus) under ambient conditions. The area is geographically located between 11°35'N and 11°40'N latitude 37°24'E and 3°29' E longitude with a latitudinal range of 1917 above mean sea level (Shiferaw *et al.*, 2022). The average maximum and minimum temperatures during storage were 35.3 ° C and 16.3 ° C, respectively. The map for experimental locations is indicated in Figure 3.1.

Source; Mekuanint Lewoyehu *et al.* (2022)

Figure 3.1. Maps of field and storage experimental site respectively

3.2. Description of Experimental Materials

Three hybrids (Red Coach, Russet and Jambar) and one open-pollinated (Bombay Red) onion varieties were used as test crop in the study (Table 3.1). The varieties were grown following the uniform and standard agronomic practices specific for onion crop (MoARD, 2019) at research site of Woramit Horticultural Crops Training and Testing Site of Amhara Region Agricultural Research Institute during the 2023 irrigation season (January – May 2023). The pre harvest treatments were supper imposed or implement on these plants and the harvested bulbs were used for the storage experiment.

Table 3.1: Description of onion varieties used in the study.

Variety name	Year of release/registration (GC)	Area of adaptation		Maturity days	Variety type
		Altitude (m)	Rainfall (mm)		
Russet FI	2013	1500-2200	Irrigated	90	Hybrid
Red Coach FI	2015	500-2200	Irrigated	107	Hybrid
Jambar FI	2011	1000-2500	Irrigated	90	Hybrid
Bombay Red	1980	700-2000	Irrigated	110-120	Open pollinated

Source: MoARD (2019)

3.3. Treatments and Experimental Design

The storage experiment consisted of four onion varieties (Bombay Red, Red Coach, Russet and Jambar) and four pre-harvest treatments (Toppling at 70% maturity/neck fall with irrigation, toppling at 70% neck fall without irrigation, toppling at 90% necks fall and harvesting at 70% plant fall with no toppling and no irrigation (control) and data were collected at four storage durations, initial (0th week), 4th week, 8th week and 12th week. Accordingly, the experimental treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) in 4*4*4 factorial (variety, preharvest treatment and storage period) arrangements with three replications.

Table 3.2: Treatment combination used in the study.

Pre-Harvest Treatment (PHT)	Onion Varieties (V)	Storage duration			
		Initial(0)	4 weeks	8 weeks	12 weeks
Toppling at 70% maturity/neck fall with irrigation three days before harvesting (PHT 1)	Russet FI (V1)	Pht1V1S0	Pht1V1S4	Pht1V1S8	Pht1V1S12
	Jembar (V2)	Pht1V2S0	Pht1V2S4	Pht1V2S8	Pht1V2S12
	Red Coach (V3)	Pht1V3S0	Pht1V3S4	Pht1V3S8	Pht1V3S12
	Bombay Red (V4)	Pht1V4S0	Pht1V4S4	Pht1V4S8	Pht1V4s12
Toppling when 90% of necks fall over without irrigation (PHT 2)	Russet FI (V1)	Pht2V1S0	Pht2V1S4	Pht2V1S8	Pht2V1S12
	Jembar (V2)	Pht2V2S0	Pht2V2S4	Pht2V2S8	Pht2V2S12
	Red Coach (V3)	Pht2V3S0	Pht2V3S4	Pht2V3S8	Pht2V3S12
	Bombay Red (V4)	Pht2V4S0	Pht2V4S4	Pht2V4S8	Pht2V4S12
Toppling at 70% neck fall without irrigation (PHT 3)	Russet FI (V1)	Pht3V1S0	Pht3V1S4	Pht3V1S8	Pht3V1S12
	Jembar (V2)	Pht3V2S0	Pht3V2S4	Pht3V2S8	Pht3V2S12
	Red Coach (V3)	Pht3V3S0	Pht3V3S4	Pht3V3S8	Pht3V3S12
	Bombay Red (V4)	Pht3V4S0	Pht3V4S4	Pht3V4S8	Pht3V4S12
Control (Harvesting at 70% plant fall with no toppling and no irrigation (PHT 4)	Russet FI (V1)	Pht4V1S0	Pht4V1S4	Pht4V1S8	Pht4V1S12
	Jembar (V2)	Pht4V2S0	Pht4V2S4	Pht4V2S8	Pht4V2S12
	Red Coach (V3)	Pht4V3S0	Pht4V3S4	Pht4V3S8	Pht4V3S12
	Bombay Red (V4)	Pht4V4S0	Pht4V4S4	Pht4V4S8	Pht4V4S12

3.4. Experimental Procedure

Pre-harvest treatments were superimposed on onion varieties grown in Woramit Horticultural Crops Training and Testing Site during the 2023 irrigation season. Onion plants were grown following uniform and standard agronomic practices specific for onion crop (MoARD, 2019) except the pre-treatments. In all cases, irrigation was ceased a week prior to implementing the toppling procedure. Toppling was done manually by trampling the plants and harvesting was done by pulling the plants at onion neck and shaking off the excess soils.

The storage experiment was done from May 2023 up to August 2023 depending on pre harvest treatments where harvesting date was delayed because of the implemented pre-harvest treatments.

Harvesting took place seven days after the implementation of the toppling treatment. After harvesting, bulbs were cured for five days under shade at an ambient temperature of 26.75 °C. Once cured, the onion tops were removed, and the bulbs were sorted for their uniformity for the storage experiment. Only uniform and marketable onion bulbs without any damages were used for storage experiment. About 5 kg of the selected bulbs (40 sample onion bulbs) from each treatment were stored in a Diffused Light Storage room. Onion bulbs were stored for three months, from early May to August where data were collected in a monthly interval depending on the parameters collected. Additionally, ten tagged bulbs were designated for destructive data collection to measure firmness and Total Soluble Solids (TSS). Daily air

temperatures and relative humidity of the storage rooms were recorded using a thermo-hygrometer.

3.5. Data collection

3.5.1. Bulb quality parameters

Bulb firmness (N): - It was recorded by a portable fruit penetrometer (GY-4 model S/N G2001707622). The first onion layer was removed and the whole bulb was penetrated from two opposite sides of the equatorial area of the bulb. The average of the two measurements was taken in every month for further analysis.

Total soluble solid (%): To determine the TSS of the sample, onion bulb was crushed, and aliquot was extracted. TSS was determined by refractometer by placing 1 to 2 drops of juice on the prism. Between samples, the prism of the refractometer was washed with distilled water and dried before use. The interval used in these measurements was every month during the storage period.

Physiological weight loss (PWL) - The physiological weight loss of onion bulbs was determined according to the methods described by Waskar *et al.* (1999) It was determined as difference between the initial weight and successive weights and divided by the initial weight and the interval used in these measurement was every month during storage period .

$$\text{Weight loss of bulbs (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \right) * 100$$

The initial weight for physiological weight loss refers to the weight of the onion bulbs measured at the beginning of the experiment or storage period.

Percentage decay/rotten bulbs (%) - The number of decayed bulbs were counted at 1th, 2th, 3th month during Storage periods and expressed as a percentage of the total number of bulbs. Decayed bulbs were removed to avoid double counting. The number of decayed bulbs at each

storage time was taken as cumulative by addition of previously rotten bulbs (Sebsebe Zewde., 2006).

$$\text{Decay percentage (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of decayed bulbs}}{\text{Total number of bulbs}} \right) * 100$$

Percentage of sprouted bulbs (%): Percentage of bulbs sprouted bulbs were ascertained by counting the number of bulbs sprouted during the storage period and divided by the total number of bulbs and then multiplied by 100. The sprouted bulbs were discarded after each count to avoid double counting. Bulbs that sprouted and rotted at the same time were classified as sprouted (Sebsebe Woldetsadik and Seyoum Workneh, 2010). The number of sprouted bulbs at each storage time was taken as cumulative by addition of previously sprouted bulbs.

$$\text{Sprouted percentage (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of sprouted bulbs}}{\text{Total number of bulbs}} \right) * 100$$

Marketable bulbs percentage (%): was subjectively assessed according to the methods described by Mohammed *et al.* (1999). The numbers of marketable onion bulbs at each stage of storage time were counted and expressed as a percentage to the total number of bulbs using the formula below.

$$\text{Marketable bulbs (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of marketable bulbs}}{\text{Total number of stored bulbs}} \right) * 100$$

3.6. Temperature and Relative humidity in Onion Storage Structure

Air temperatures and relative humidity of the storage rooms were recorded using a thermo hygrometer. The readings were taken daily interval (Figure 3.2). The recorded atmospheric conditions in the storage facility exhibit some variability throughout the storage period. The average atmospheric temperature and relative humidity in the storage structure (DLS) during the storage period of onion are presented in Figure 3.2. The maximum and minimum

temperatures recorded were 27.82°C in May and 23.5 °C in August, respectively. The average temperature throughout the storage period ranged from 23.5 °C to 19.72 °C. Relative humidity levels also vary, with the minimum of 33.7% in May indicating relatively dry conditions, while the maximum of 86.65% in August suggests higher humidity levels.

Figure 3.2: Average atmospheric temperature and relative humidity in DLS during storage period of onion in 2023

3.6. Data analysis

The collected data was initially checked for all ANOVA assumptions (normality, homogeneity, and residual). The data was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC MIXED procedure of SAS computer software version 9.4. Preharvest treatments and onion varieties were considered as fixed effects and storage durations were random effects due to mixed model combined analysis. When ANOVA showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$), the mean separation was carried out using the least significant difference (LSD) (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Effects of Pre-Harvest Treatments on Postharvest Loss and Quality of Onion Bulbs

4.1.1. Bulb sprouting percentage

The combined analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration as well as two-way interactions of variety x storage period and storage period x preharvest treatments significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced the bulb sprouting percentage of onion in the storage. Conversely, the two-way interaction of variety x preharvest treatments and the three-way interaction of variety x preharvest treatments x storage duration did not influence ($P > 0.05$) this parameter (Appendix Table 1).

Bombay Red variety recorded the highest sprouting percentage (10.25%) followed by the variety Red Coach (8.52%) during the three month storage duration, while the lowest was recorded from the variety Russet (6.99%) and Jambar (7.13%) across storage duration of three months (Figure 4.2). The difference between varieties for sprouting percentage is obviously associated with the genetic variations of the varieties on their dormancy characteristics. Variation in sprouting potential of onion varieties was also reported by other researchers (Adamicki, 2005; Gebisa Bededa, 2017; Gateri, 2019).

Bulbs that were toppled at 90% plant fall recorded the lowest sprouting percentage (5.6 %) while those bulbs harvested at 70% plant fall (without toppling, and irrigation), toppled at 70% maturity and irrigated before three days of harvested recorded the highest sprouting percentages of 9.63 % and 10.11%, respectively (Figure 4.1). Toppling is an important cultural practice of onion production, which facilitates the drying of outer skin of onion bulbs and thus reduces the risk of sprouting during storage. Toppling at 90% neck fall and 70% neck fall without irrigation of onion plants reduced bulb sprouting by 80.5% and 45.8% compared to the harvesting at 70% neck fall without toppling (control) .

As the storage duration increases, there is a linear increase in the sprouting percentage of onions. Specifically, the highest sprouting percentage was observed in bulbs stored for 12 weeks, followed by those stored for eight and four weeks. The increase of sprouting as the storage period extend may caused by the rise of relative humidity and reduction of temperature in storage room during storage period (Figure 3.2).

Similar to the present findings, different researchers also reported that proper toppling reduces bulb sprouting during storage (Bizuayehu Desta *et al.*, 2021; Gonzalez *et al.*,2020; Garcia *et al.* 2021; Smith *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, toppling of onion plants at early stages might lead to the production of bulbs that are not fully matured, which may potentially be more susceptible to premature sprouting during storage (Khire *et al.*, 2019). Application of irrigation at late stage of onion increases bulb moisture content, which creates conducive environment for sprouting during storage as indicated in the present study and other researchers (Gorreapti *et al.*, 2017, Patel and Gupta, 2021). Generally, physiological weight loss, rotting, and sprouting, increases the postharvest losses and ultimately reduce the shelf life of onion (Bizuayehu Desta *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 4.1: Effects of variety and pre-harvest treatments on sprouting percentage of onion in storage (combined over storage durations)

4.1.2. Decay percentage

The combined analysis of variance across storage duration showed that the main effects of variety, pre harvest treatment and storage duration as well as their two-way and three-way interactions significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced the bulb decay percentage of onion in the storage (Appendix Table 2).

The highest decay percentage (17.63%) was observed from variety Bombay Red followed by variety Red Coach (13.54%) while the lowest was observed from variety Russet (11.54%) and Jamber (12.01%) throughout the storage duration. When compared to the Bombay Red variety, the Russet showed a 53.97% lower decay rate (figure 4.2). The present results indicated that hybrid onion varieties generally have relative higher storability compared to open-pollinated varieties like Bombay Red. In this regard, Diaz-Perez *et al.* (2003) reported that hybrid onion varieties often have a longer shelf life than open-pollinated onions due to

their thicker and dried skins, which help them to protect the bulbs from mechanical damages during handling and storage that intern reduce the incidence of disease infection. Differences in decay percentage observed in the present study are obviously associated with the genetic makeup of varieties. Differences among onion varieties towards spoilage/decay percentage were also observed by various researchers (Stuber *et al.*, 1992; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2014; Singh *et al.*, 2015; Gebisa Bededa, 2017; Mota *et al.*, 2019; Randhawa *et al.*, 2022).

Among pre-harvest treatments, the lowest decay percentage (10.55%) was recorded from bulbs, topped at 90% maturity followed by toppling at 70% maturity (12.5%). On the other hand, the highest decay percentage (16.59%) was recorded from bulbs harvested at 70% maturity (control) (Figure 4.2). **As the storage duration increases, there is a linear increase in the onion decay percentage was observed in bulbs stored for 12 weeks. This could be attributed to the increase of relative humidity in the storage room during storage period, which leads to condensation and can promote mold, fungi growth and leads to sprouting, decay and rotting of onion bulbs (Figure 3.2).**

Toppling at the right time of maturity is an important agronomic practice that helps to facilitate the drying of the outer skin of bulbs leading to reduced decay, shrinking, and sprouting in the storage as indicated in the present study. Toppling at 90 and 70% maturity reduced the bulb decay percentage by 57% and 38%, respectively, compared to un-topped harvested at 70% maturity (Figure 4.2). Similarly, regulated irrigation, especially at the time of maturity, is also critical to reduce the moisture content of the bulbs (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2019). Irrigation on topped and harvested at 70% maturity in the present study increased the decay by 20% compared to non-irrigated and but topped at 70% maturity (Figure 4.2). Harvesting the bulbs too early may also lead to more decay in the storage due to un-matured bulbs. Additionally, the decay percentage of onions after harvest showed a trend of increasing throughout the storage length (Figure 4.2). This trend can be attributed as initially, onions may undergo physiological changes and metabolic activities that make them more susceptible to decay during the storage (Coolong., 2007).

Figure 4.2: Decay percentage of onion bulbs under different pre-harvest treatments (Combined over the storage durations)

Similarly, the highest decay percentage (22.87%) was recorded from the Bombay Red variety untoppled and unirrigated but harvested at 70% of maturity. Conversely, the lowest decay percentages were recorded from the Jambar (6.48%) and Russet (8.43%) varieties topped at 90% maturity, respectively (Table 4.1). Maintaining an appropriate moisture level in bulbs, particularly during storage, is essential to prevent favorable conditions for fungal growth and decay (Khire *et al.*, 2019; Patel and Gupta, 2021). The lowest decay percentage on bulbs topped at 90% maturity in the present study is therefore obviously associated with drying of the outer skin of the bulbs that leads to the reduced disease infection in storage (Getenesh Nega *et al.*, 2015). Generally, topping at different stages of maturity contributes to the reduction of onion bulb decay during post-harvest handling and storage. Proper handling techniques, including careful sorting and regular inspection, can also help minimize damage and prolong the shelf life of onions.

Table 4.1: Interaction effects of variety and preharvest treatments on bulb decay percentage (data combined over the storage duration)

Onion Varieties	Toppling at 90 % neck fall	Toppling at 70% neck fall, without irrigation	Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Control (un toppling, un irrigation): harvested at 70% maturity
Russet	8.43hi	9.81gh	11.48efg	13.15cde
Jambar	6.48i	10.37fgh	13.15cde	15.09c
Red Coach	10.9fg	14.26cd	13.70cd	12.31def
Bombay Red	13.43cde	13.1cde	18.15b	22.87a
P-values			***	
LSD (0.05)			2.8	
CV (%)			25.63	
SE±			0.34	

Where; ***=very highly significant at $p<0.0001$; ** = highly significant at $P<0.01$; means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at 5% probability level according to LSD test; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation and SE = standard error

4.1.3. Total Soluble Solid

The combined analysis revealed that onion variety ($P<0.0001$) and its interaction with preharvest treatment ($p<0.0001$) influenced the total soluble solids (TSS) content of the stored onion bulbs. Similarly, the main effect of variety, pre-harvest treatment and storage duration significantly influenced ($p<0.001$) the TSS of the stored onion bulbs. However, the interactions between preharvest treatment x storage duration, variety x storage duration and preharvest treatment x storage duration x variety did not show any influence on the onion total soluble solids (TSS) (Appendix Table 3).

Bombay Red variety recorded the highest TSS value compared to the tested hybrid onion varieties throughout the storage period (Figure 4.3). Similarly, Bombay Red variety toppled at 90% recorded the highest TSS value (Table 4.2). The differences among varieties for TSS may be due to the variations on the genetic makeup. In this regard, Choje *et al.* (2007) and Mohammed and Gaafar (2005) reported the variations in the TSS content of onion varieties, which was attributed to their genetic variations.

The higher Total Soluble Solid (TSS) content of Bombay Red could be associated with late maturity compared to high-yielding varieties (Rai *et al.*, 2006). Extended maturation periods allow for prolonged accumulation and conversion of starches into sugars, resulting in higher TSS levels at harvest. In addition, low-yielder onion varieties possess genetic traits that favor the accumulation of sugars or other soluble solids in the bulb. These genetic factors may influence metabolic pathways involved in sugar synthesis, transport, and storage within the plant tissues (Fait *et al.*, 2008 and Kader, 2008). Similar with the results of the present study, Mallor and Sales (2012) indicated that varieties with higher bulb yields have lower TSS content compared with varieties with the lowest yields due to the production of small-sized bulbs. Relatively higher TSS in open-pollinated tomato varieties is also reported compared to the hybrid once, which could be bred for specific traits such as better storability, yield potential, and uniformity rather than higher TSS (Willmitzer, 2001; Giovannoni, 2004; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2013; Berno *et al.*, 2014). Patel and Lee, (2019) also reported the interaction between variety and toppling stages influences the TSS content of onion bulbs differently. Kothari *et al.* (2020), on their studies concluded that onions with a higher sugar content might result in a higher weight loss during storage as a result of increased respiration rates. A higher level of TSS could result in more active metabolic processes, resulting in greater weight loss as sugars are used during respiration, which could lead to weight loss. Furthermore, Patel *et al.* (2020) indicated that different onion varieties display various levels of TSS. Furthermore, some varieties genetically have higher TSS, which might correlate with better storage characteristics, while others might have lower TSS but possess traits that contribute to improved storability.

In general, there was a gradual increasing trend of TSS until the end of the fourth week of storage then after TSS of bulbs showed a decreasing trend as the storage period prolonged (Figure 4.3). The increase of TSS up to the end of the fourth week of storage might be associated with the conversion of polysaccharides into soluble form of sugars. After the 4th week of storage, the proportional rise in carbohydrate metabolism and respiration rate leads to low TSS. According to Chávez-Mendoza *et al.* (2016) the sugar metabolism is closely linked to the breaking of dormancy and the start of sprouting of onion. Similarly, Chope *et al.* (2012) reported that changes during storage are related to respiration and re-mobilization of

carbohydrates to provide energy for the development of sprouts, which is associated with the sudden reduction of TSS.

Figure 4.3: Total Soluble Solid (TSS) of onion as influenced by variety and pre-harvest treatments combined over the storage durations.

4.1.4. Bulb firmness

The combined analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, pre harvest treatment and storage duration influenced ($p < 0.0001$) the bulb firmness. In addition, the interaction between variety x preharvest treatment showed highly significant ($p < 0.001$) effect on bulb firmness across storage durations. However, the other two way and three-way interaction did not influence ($p > 0.05$) the bulb firmness across storage durations (Appendix Table 4).

Bulb firmness was generally decreased as the storage period extends. Bulbs of Jamber (9.48 Newton) and Russet (9.32 Newton) varieties had relatively higher firmness over the combined

storage duration compared to other varieties. Similarly, bulbs from plants topped at 90% neck fall recorded the highest firmness (9.90 Newton) compared to other pre-harvest treatments (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Main effects of variety and pre harvest treatment on firmness of onion bulbs (data combined over the storage duration)

Likewise, Jambar (10.84 Newton) and Russet (10.6 Newton) varieties topped at 90% neck fall recorded the highest bulb firmness value (Table 4.2).

Bulb firmness is an important feature that enhances the shelf life of a given onion varieties, which could be associated with the genetic makeup of the varieties (Smith *et al.*, 2020). In this regard, Romo and Maria (2021) reported that different onion varieties possess distinct genetic characteristics that can influence bulb firmness as indicated in the present study.

Khire *et al.* (2019) reported that different toppling stages also affect bulb maturity and dry matter accumulation. Bulbs harvested at 90% neck fall might have higher dry matter content

with more completed bulb maturity and reduced moisture content, which contributes for increased bulb firmness. On the other hand, irrigation after toppling increases the bulb moisture content that affects the bulb firmness as indicated in the present study (toppling at 70% + irrigation). Such excessive moisture could potentially lead to softer bulbs (Patel and Gupta, 2021). The decrease in firmness during storage is related to biochemical reactions of cell wall degradation (Chávez-Mendoza *et al.*, 2016). This could be attributed to a progressive decline in the structural integrity and firmness of onion bulbs over time due to the loss in moisture loss through transpiration and respiration processes. As the moisture levels decrease, the cells in the onion bulbs lose turgor pressure, leading to softening of the tissues leading in firmness losses. In addition, enzymatic activities such as cell wall degrading enzymes (e.g., pectinases) contribute to the breakdown of cell walls and other structural components, resulting in softer bulbs over time (Adams and Hicks, 2005; Kader, 2008).

As the storage duration increases, there is a decrease in the onion firmness was observed in bulbs stored for 12 weeks. This could be attributed to a progressive decline in the structural integrity and firmness of onion bulbs over time due to the loss in moisture loss through transpiration and respiration processes (Figure 4.4).

Table 4.2: Interaction effects of varieties and pre-harvest treatments on total soluble solid and firmness (combined over storage duration)

Pre-harvest treatment	Variety	TSS (%)	Firmness (Newton)
Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Russet	7.14ef	8.72cde
	Jambar	7.60cdef	8.12efg
	Red Coach	7.57cdef	7.89fg
	Bombay Red	11.14b	7.76h
Toppling at 90 % neck fall	Russet	7.05ef	10.6a
	Jambar	8.30cd	10.84a
	Red Coach	8.30cd	9.56b
	Bombay Red	12.95a	8.61def
Toppling at 70 % neck fall, without irrigation	Russet	8.19cd	9.50bc
	Jambar	8.36cd	9.67b
	Red Coach	8.45c	8.29efg
	Bombay red	7.92cde	8.62def
Control (un toppling, un irrigation)	Russet	6.63f	8.47efg
	Jambar	8.47c	9.27bcd
	Red Coach	7.35def	8.66def
	Bombay Red	11.44b	7.98efg
P-values		***	**
LSD (0.05)		1.03	0.7
CV (%)		16.2	11.08
SE±		0.16	0.13

Where; ***=very highly significant at $P<0.0001$; ** = highly significant at $P<0.01$; means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different at 5% probability level according to LSD test; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation and SE = standard error

4.1.5. Bulb weight loss (%)

The analysis of variance showed that the main effects of variety, pre harvest treatment and storage duration influenced ($p<0.001$) the weight loss of bulbs. The two-way interaction between variety and storage duration also highly significantly ($p<0.001$) influenced the bulb weight loss. However, the interaction of the variety x pre harvest treatment, pre harvest treatment x storage duration and variety x pre harvest treatment x storage duration did not affect ($p>0.05$) weight loss percentage of onion (Appendix Table 5).

Weight loss of bulbs was generally increased as the storage period increased where bulbs of Jambar (1.24%, 2.52%, and 5.24%) and Russet (1.31%, 3.09% and 5.37%) varieties recorded

the lowest weight loss during the storage periods of 4th, 8th and 12th weeks respectively compared to other varieties respectively. The increase in weight loss would be associated with higher respiration rate. Similarly, bulbs from plants toppled at 90% neck fall recorded the lowest weight loss 1.51%, 3.46% and 4.74 % at 4th, 8th and 12th weeks' storage lengths respectively compared to other pre-treatments (Figure 4.5).

Postharvest loss in onion is among others expressed in terms of weight loss leading to losses in the economics of smallholder farmers. Choosing appropriate varieties that have high storability is therefore necessary to reduce postharvest losses in onion storage. In this regard, bulbs of hybrid varieties, Jamber and Russet recorded less weight loss percentage throughout storage duration, which could be related to their genetic makeup. Hybrid varieties of onion are mainly bred to have thicker skins, which help protect onion bulbs from mechanical damage and water loss leading to less weight loss. Therefore, hybrid onion varieties often have longer shelf life than open-pollinated onions (Tabussam *et al.*, 2022).

Generally, weight loss of onion bulbs increased over a three-month storage duration, which differ with variety and pre-harvest treatments (Figure 4.5). Toppling facilitates the drying of outer skin of bulbs that in turn reduces water and weight losses. The reduced weight loss on onions from plants toppled at 90% neck fall could be therefore associated with lower moisture content of the bulbs due to extended physiological maturity. Likewise, Khire *et al.* (2019) found that bulbs harvested at 90% maturity stages recorded reduced weight loss in storage. Research also observed low incidence of skin rot, lower weight loss, and more marketable grades of bulbs, reduced post-harvest diseases and strong outer skins when onions were harvested at 80-100% leaf fall (Sebsebe Woldetsadik and Seyoum Workneh, 2010; Akrofi *et al.*, 2016; Eshel *et al.*, 2014).

Irrigation practices before harvesting significantly influence sprouting and weight loss of onion varieties (Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.5). Accordingly, irrigation soon before harvesting negatively affects the post-harvest quality and storage characteristics of onion. This could be attributed to the availability of excess water in the matured bulbs that may favor regrowth of new shoots and weight loss of the onion bulbs. The results are in agreement with Patel *et al.*,

(2020) who observed that onions irrigated close to the harvesting have excess initial moisture leading to higher weight loss compared to un-irrigated bulbs during storage. A combination of appropriate topping techniques to initiate drying and controlled irrigation practices before harvesting aids in achieving the optimal moisture content in bulbs, reducing weight loss and sprouting during storage (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2019), which is in line with the results of the present study.

Figure 4.5: Main effects of variety and pre harvest treatment on weight loss of onion bulbs (separate to storage duration)

4.1.6. Marketable bulb percentage

The percentage of marketable bulb was influenced ($P < 0.001$) by main effects of variety, pre harvest treatment and storage durations and their interaction combined over the storage level (Appendix Table 6).

Among onion varieties, Russet (82.58%) and Jambar (81.88%) maintained the highest marketable bulbs. On the other hand, the lowest marketable bulb (73.13%) was observed from variety Bombay Red (Figure 4.6). Among the pre harvest treatments the highest marketable bulbs (84.87%) were recorded from onion bulbs toppled at 90 % neck fall followed by toppled at 70% neck fall. However, the lowest percentage of marketable bulbs was recorded from bulbs harvested at 70% neck fall without toppling and irrigation(control) (74.8%) and toppled at 70% neck fall and irrigated (75.91%) (Figure 4.6). In the interaction effect, Russet (85.55%) and Jambar (88.61%) varieties toppled at 90% neck fall recorded the highest marketable bulb percentage combined over the storage duration (Table 4.3).

Selecting the appropriate onion variety can significantly impact marketable bulb yield, potentially leading to an increase of up to 15% (Figure 4.6). This underscores the importance of careful variety selection for onion growers. Sprouting, a crucial indicator of onion bulb unmarketability began after four weeks of storage period and continued until the end of the three-month. The highest marketable bulbs from hybrid varieties like Jambar and Russet, compared to open pollinated variety Bombay Red throughout the storage duration can be due to the genetic makeup of the crop. Thus, the choice of onion variety and the implementation of appropriate pre-harvest treatments, onions can be stored for a month and above durations, ensuring their marketability and quality over time.

Figure 4.6: Main effects of variety and pre-harvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage (data combined over the storage durations)

Table 4.3: Interaction effects of variety and Preharvest treatments on marketable bulb percentage combined across storage durations.

Onion Varieties	Toppling at 90 % neck fall	Toppling at 70% neck fall, without irrigation	Toppling at 70% neck fall with irrigation	Control (un toppling, un irrigation): harvested at 70% maturity
Russet	85.55ab	83.05b	78.33cd	77.77de
Jambar	88.61a	82.50b	76.94def	73.88f
Red Coach	81.94bc	76.94def	74.44ef	76.94def
Bombay Red	77.77de	75.83def	68.33g	65.00g
P-values			***	
LSD (0.05)			3.81	
CV (%)			3.11	
SE±			0.73	

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Conclusion

The results of the present study clearly showed that variety and pre-harvest treatment influenced the postharvest quality of onion bulbs including sprouting, decay, weight loss, firmness, TSS and marketability of onion bulbs in storage. Jambar and Russet varieties sprouted relatively late and recorded the lowest losses in bulb weight and decay percentage compared to Bombay Red and Red Coach varieties. Moreover, the bulbs of these varieties were relatively firm and recorded the highest marketable percentage after three months of storage. Similarly, toppling of onion plants positively influences the postharvest quality and shelf life of onion bulbs in storage while irrigation some days before harvesting negatively influenced these parameters. Bulbs toppled at 90% neck fall sprouted later and recorded reduced decay percentage and weight loss. Moreover, the bulbs were more firm and had better total soluble solids with the highest proportion of marketable bulbs in storage.

5.2. Recommendation

Selection of suitable onion variety and implementation of appropriate pre-harvest treatments is necessary to reduce postharvest losses of onion bulbs in the storage. Toppling at 90% neck fall and using Jambar and Russet hybrid onion varieties and storing them in Defused Light Storage enable farmers to store onion bulbs for 4 weeks without a significant postharvest loss,

which can be recommended for Bahir Dar Zuria district and areas with similar agro-ecology. As the work is limited to one season and location, it is suggested to repeat the study in multilocation and season.

CHAPTER SIX: REFERENCES

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APPENDICES

Appendix Table 1: Analysis of variance for bulb sprouting percentage

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	21.00	6.02	<i>0.0032</i>	*
Varieties (VAR	3	110.86	31.13	<i><.0001</i>	***
Preharvest treatment (PRHT)	3	206.23	57.92	<i><.0001</i>	***

Storage duration (STD)	3	1729.68	67.01	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	5.51	1.55	0.1281	Ns
VAR*STD	9	13.53	3.80	0.0003	**
PRHT*STD	9	25.16	7.07	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	2.90	0.82	0.7246	Ns

Where; *** = very highly significant at P<0.0001; highly significant at p<0.001; Ns = non-significant at P>0.05 and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 2: Analysis of variance for bulb decay percentage

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	56.01	1.53	0.2198	Ns
Varieties (VAR	3	1123.32	62.12	<.0001	***
Preharvest treatment (PRHT)	3	1027.48	56.82	<.0001	***
Storage duration (STD)	3	19302.48	148.26	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	466.26	8.59	<.0001	***
VAR*STD	9	533.85	9.84	<.0001	***
PRHT*STD	9	451.90	8.33	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	292.30	1.80	0.014	**

Where; *** = very highly significant at P<0.0001; highly significant at p<0.001; Ns = non-significant at P>0.05 and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 3 : Analysis of variance for total soluble solid

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	1.85	0.97	0.3833	Ns
Varieties (VAR	3	121.04	62.91	<.0001	***
Preharvest treatment (PRHT)	3	8.15	4.24	0.0068	**
Storage duration (STD)	3	36.96	19.08	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	18.73	9.74	<.0001	***
VAR*STD	9	1.63	0.85	0.5733	Ns
PRHT*STD	9	0.77	0.40	0.9324	Ns
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	0.71	0.37	0.9980	Ns

Where; *** = very highly significant at P<0.0001; highly significant at p<0.001; Ns = non-significant at P>0.05 and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 4 : Analysis of variance for firmness

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	11.43	9.47	<.0001	***
Varieties (VAR	3	20.90	17.01	<.0001	***
Preharvest treatment	3	21.83	28.23	<.0001	***

(PRHT)					
Storage duration (STD)	3	113.88	21.72	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	4.04	2.44	0.0013	**
VAR*STD	9	0.50	0.04	0.9216	Ns
PRHT*STD	9	0.23	0.16	0.9941	Ns
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	0.51	0.05	0.9936	Ns

Where; *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.0001$; highly significant at $p < 0.001$; Ns = non-significant at $P > 0.05$ and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 5 : Analysis of variance for weight loss percentage

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	24.13	4.02	0.0203	*
Varieties (VAR)	3	131.18	22.1	<.0001	***
Preharvest treatment (PRHT)	3	32.40	5.43	0.0015	**
Storage duration (STD)	3	107750.38	2609.23	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	11.52	1.93	0.0548	Ns
VAR*STD	9	17.19	2.88	0.0042	**
PRHT*STD	9	4.92	0.83	0.5984	Ns
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	1.93	0.32	0.9994	Ns

Where; *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.0001$; highly significant at $p < 0.001$; Ns = non-significant at $P > 0.05$ and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Table 6: Analysis of variance for marketable bulb percentage

Source of Variation	DF	Mean square	F- value	Pr > F	P- value
Replication	2	49.01	3.34	0.0385	*
Varieties (VAR)	3	887.26	102.11	<.0001	***
Preharvest treatment (PRHT)	3	1047.60	120.57	<.0001	***
Storage duration (STD)	3	14401.92	230.13	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT	9	62.01	7.14	<.0001	***

VAR*STD	9	121.27	13.96	<.0001	***
PRHT*STD	9	128.93	14.84	<.0001	***
VAR*PRHT*STD	27	15.69	1.81	0.015	**

Where; *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.0001$; highly significant at $p < 0.001$; Ns = non-significant at $P > 0.05$ and DF = Degree of freedom

Appendix Figure 0.1: Topped onion plants and the practice of harvesting and selecting marketable onion bulbs

Appendix Figure 2: Data collection on quality parameters

Appendix Figure 3 : Deffused light storage room

BIOGRAPHIC SKECH

The author, Fentahun Assefa Mekonnen was born on 08 December 1991 E.C in Debre Elias Woreda, East Gojjam Zone of Amhara Region, Ethiopia. He attended his elementary School at *Degolema Deberemetemake* primary school from 1997 to 2005 E.C. He completed his secondary and preparatory school education at *Debre Elias* General Secondary and Preparatory School from 2005 to 2009 E.C. After completed his elementary and secondary education, he joined Wolkite University in 2010 E.C and graduated with the degree of Bachelor of Science (BSc) in Horticulture in 08 January, 2013 E.C. In 2014 E.C, he joined at Bahir Dar University, College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, the School of Post graduate Programs to pursue his M.Sc. degree in Horticulture.